

Part-I: Information Analysis and Presentation: An Art of Academic Writing

Siddhartha Shankar Ray

Often we come across requests for supply of materials regarding Scientific Writing while most of them relate to designing the study which are often survey research and involve interview and/or questionnaire. Unfortunately, it is observed that the individuals have urge for doing some study but it appears that they often lack the knowledge how to start with it where development of a suitable questionnaire become the first stepping stone. Here starts the problem. In the days of cyber technology, the easiest way is to get 'links' to such materials from others who had developed one earlier and successfully completed the study either for the dissertations or for publication of articles. The activities now remain just to copy & paste the available materials! Apparently it needs least effort in devising the prototype of a questionnaire and the studies often become stereotype and repetitive. As it becomes a practice, it leaves no alternative to the new worker but to depend upon others' used materials throughout his/her career. Admittedly, one can tide over the examination or can even publish an article to glorify his/her resume but actually s/he learns nothing new. On the stead, if one tries to develop his/her own research strategies, it helps in several big ways; first s/he develops a better understanding of the issue, s/he develops the skill of analyzing an issue from different points of views some of which might have missed by his/her peers; gains confidence – a lifelong achievement which propels him/her to write many excellent research reports or articles in later years as s/he matures and ultimately, can develop a research strategy exclusively original!! It may seem to be difficult to start with and one may be time-constrained to finish the project but by taking short-cut routes s/he commits an irreparable lifelong mistake. It's like walking with the help of supporting devices throughout one's entire life! As a person undertakes a study, mentally s/he prepares a plan purpose, of what he is doing, why is he doing, what he is supposed to identify and highlight, how significant his/her study will be and how is s/he going to present the findings and what will be the inference. This applies equally to diverse subject fields like Public Health, Sociology and Library related activities. There should be study samples and statistical applications in explaining the issues. If such endeavours are stale repetitions of earlier works (except in the case of highlighting the difference over time) the novelty and importance of work and most importantly becomes quite short of expectations.

How to Cite this Article

Ray, S. S. (2015). Part-I: Information Analysis and Presentation: An Art of Academic Writing. *LIS Links Newsletter*, 1(5), 1.